

Temperature dependence of Young's modulus of kaolin-based silicate ceramics with mullite addition

Petra Šimonová^{a,*}, Eva Gregorová^a, Willi Pabst^a, Daria Viazun^a, Petr Bezdička^b

^a Department of Glass and Ceramics, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague (UCT Prague), Prague, Czechia

^b Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Czech Academy of Sciences, Řež, Czechia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

High-alumina refractories
Elastic properties (Young's modulus)
Impulse excitation technique (IET)

ABSTRACT

The temperature dependence of Young's modulus of kaolin-based silicate ceramics with mullite addition fired at 1100, 1200, 1300, 1400 and 1500 °C is investigated using the impulse excitation technique (IET). A minimum is observed at around 1200 °C, followed by a steep increase to ~120 GPa and a stepwise discontinuity at ~1270 °C to final values of 60–70 GPa, which are retained up to 1500 °C. This peculiar behavior can be explained by the assumption that the glass melt is able to heal pre-existent microcracks and the softening of the glass phase leads to a splitting of the resonant frequency peak, i.e. a decoupling of the flexural vibrations of the interconnected mullite skeleton (67–75 wt. %) and the interskeletal glassy phase (24–28 wt. %), which finally leads to a discontinuity when the mullite crystals become disconnected and the microstructure of the material changes from bicontinuous to matrix-inclusion type.

1. Introduction

Kaolin-based silicate ceramics are materials that have been used for centuries, e.g. in the form of porcelain, where quartz and feldspar is added to achieve densification during firing by liquid-phase sintering with a high content of glass phase (vitrification). Due to the presence of mullite as the main crystalline phase, these materials can have many excellent properties but due to the presence of alkaline ions they are not refractory. On the other hand, alkali-free mixtures based on pure kaolin or other alkali-free clays (fireclay) have been among the first successful refractories for industrial applications. Also here mullite is the key phase, but even in these materials a glass phase is present and has to be taken into account for property assessment. A prominent place among these traditional industrial applications are regenerators and recuperators, in which these materials are used to accumulate and exchange thermal energy transported via flowing gas streams [1]. Much more recently, these refractory materials have come into play also as possible candidates for high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) of solar energy. In particular, due to their low cost and competitive properties (e.g. high temperature strength and creep resistance, low thermal expansion), mullite-based materials [2,3] and their composites with cordierite [4–6] are, together with anorthite-based ceramics [7–9], possibly promising competitors against alumina-based composites

[10–12], SiC-containing ceramics [13,14] and silica refractories [15,16].

Of course, for an assessment of kaolin-based silicate ceramics for HT-TES applications the high-temperature behavior must be reliably known, including the temperature dependence of mechanical properties such as Young's modulus during heating and cooling. For this purpose, the impulse excitation technique (IET) [17,18] is a perfectly suitable method. In a recent paper of our group [19] the IET has been used to study the evolution of the Young's modulus for three types of Czech kaolins during firing to 1250 and 1400 °C. It has been shown that all important processes occurring during the firing of kaolin, i.e. the dehydroxylation from kaolinite to metakaolinite, the subsequent transformation of metakaolinite into the defective Al-Si-spinel phase and the final transformation of this almost X-ray amorphous phase into mullite can be conveniently monitored via the IET. These investigations confirmed many of the findings obtained for other clays via in situ ultrasonic echography by Pialy et al. [20] and by thermomechanical analysis by Štubňa, Trnák, Húlan and coworkers [21–26]. However, all these papers by other authors are limited to temperatures below 1200 °C and most of them [20–23,26] do not report the cooling branches. Heating and cooling branches measured via the IET during firing have been reported by Nigay et al. up to 1100 °C [27] and Húlan et al. up to 1200 °C [28] but for illitic clays, not for kaolin. Only very few works of

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: simonovb@vscht.cz (P. Šimonová).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2025.100774>

Received 23 October 2024; Received in revised form 14 February 2025; Accepted 26 March 2025

Available online 28 March 2025

2666-5395/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of European Ceramic Society. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

this type have been focused on kaolin [29,30]. Other authors have investigated the evolution of Young's modulus by firing only via IET measurements at room temperature after firing [31–34], and it seems that only one work has performed this task via three-point bending measurements at room temperature after firing [35]. The majority of these works agrees that the most significant changes of Young's modulus are expected for firing at temperatures higher than 1000 °C. This behavior of kaolin-based silicate ceramics is very much different from silicate ceramics based on quartz-containing illitic clays [36] or on feldspar and quartz [37,38] where the most important changes in Young's modulus (as monitored by the IET) occur at temperatures far below 1000 °C and are severely affected by the low-high-quartz transition.

The aforementioned work of our group [19] reports the evolution of Young's modulus of pure kaolin-based ceramics, as measured by the IET, up to 1250 and 1400 °C during heating, as well as the cooling branches, which are representative for the temperature dependence of Young's modulus after firing. However, we are not aware of similar measurements for kaolin-based ceramics with mullite addition, in analogy to the temperature dependence of Young's modulus for mullite ceramics and alumina-mullite composite ceramics that has been investigated in our group via the IET during thermal cycling (heating and cooling) [39,40] up to 1500 °C. Compared to pure kaolin-based ceramics, kaolin-based ceramics with mullite addition may be expected to show improved high-temperature properties, while compared to pure mullite- or mullite-alumina ceramics they should be cheaper. Therefore, the present work aims at characterizing the temperature dependence of Young's modulus for kaolin-based ceramics with mullite addition (20 % and 30 %), fired to different temperatures (from 1100 to 1500 °C), via IET measurements up to temperatures corresponding to the original firing temperatures. The IET results are related to changes in phase composition (as determined via X-ray diffraction / XRD quantitative phase analysis) as well as changes in bulk density and open porosity (as determined via the Archimedes method).

2. Experimental

Kaolin Sedlec Ia (Sedlecký kaolin, a.s., Czech Republic) and synthetic mullite SYMULOX M72 (Nabaltec AG, Germany) were used as the raw materials (powders). The chemical composition of these powders was characterized by X-ray fluorescence / XRF (PERFORM'X, Thermo ARL, Switzerland), the phase composition by X-ray diffraction / XRD (PANalytical X'Pert, The Netherlands) and the particle size distribution by laser diffraction (Horiba LA 960V2, Japan). Scanning electron microscopy / SEM has been performed with a LYRA3 instrument (Tescan, Czech Republic).

From these raw powders two mixtures were prepared with the weight percentages listed in Table 1. The two mixtures (K80M20 and K70M30) were prepared with sodium pyrophosphate as a dispersant (0.5 wt. % of 5 mol % solution), corundum balls were used as the grinding medium, and distilled water was used as the milling liquid. These mixtures were homogenized for 6 h on a rotary mill (Heidolph Reax 2, Germany). After homogenization, the suspension was dried at 105 °C and after drying ground into a fine powder. The samples were prepared from this powder by uniaxial pressing at 50 MPa in the shape of bars (length 100 mm, width 20 mm and height approximately 10 mm). After pressing, these samples were sintered in the temperature range from 1100 to 1500 °C with a heating rate of 2 °C/min and a dwell time of 2 h. For comparison, also pure kaolin samples (K100M0) have

Table 1

Composition of the mixtures prepared from the raw powders.

Mixture	Kaolin Sedlec Ia [wt. %]	Mullite M72 [wt. %]
K80M20	80	20
K70M30	70	30

been prepared in the same way by uniaxial pressing and sintering. After the high-temperature dwell, “free” cooling in the furnace has been applied (by switching off the heating power), i.e. the cooling rate is not controlled and the temperature exhibits a strongly non-linear decrease with time due to the thermal inertia of the furnace. However, the average cooling rate is not very much different from the heating rate (estimated range 2–3 °C/min).

After sintering, the samples were characterized by measuring linear shrinkage. Bulk density and open porosity were determined by the Archimedes method. X-ray diffraction was used to obtain the phase composition of both crystalline and amorphous phases. These measurements were performed on an X'Pert diffractometer (PANalytical, The Netherlands) with CuK α radiation with wavelength 0.154 nm, operated with 40 kV and 30 mA (line focus), a linear position sensitive PIXCel3D (Cu anode) detector and multicore optics. Both the raw powders and the sintered samples (fine powders prepared by crushing and milling of the sintered samples) were measured with Bragg-Brentano geometry for all measurements. The raw powders were measured only with a 0.04 rad Soller slit, 0.25° divergence slit and 15 mm mask, and the pattern was collected in the range from 5° to 90° 2 θ with a step size of 0.0131° with 100 s per step. The sintered samples were measured with a 0.04 rad Soller slits, 0.5° divergence slit, and 15 mm mask, and the patterns were collected in the range from 15° to 90° 2 θ with a step size of 0.0131° with 100 s per step. Qualitative phase analysis was performed with the HighScorePlus software (Malvern PANalytical, The Netherlands, version 5.2.0) [41] and the PDF-5 + 2024 database (International Centre for Diffraction Data, USA). Quantification of the experimental data was performed with the Rietveld method [42] using the Profex 4.3.6 / BGMN 4.2.23 software package for the calculations [43,44]. To determine the amorphous phase content, 20 wt. % of ZnO was added as an internal standard.

Elastic properties at room temperature were measured by the impulse excitation technique (IET) (RDFA 23, IMCE, Belgium) on the composite samples K80M20 and K70M30. Young's modulus was determined from the resonant frequency of flexural vibrations according to the relevant ASTM standards [17,18]. The temperature dependence of Young's modulus was measured by IET in a special high-temperature electrical furnace (HT1600, IMCE, Belgium). The measurement was done on samples sintered before the measurement and the temperature treatment was from room temperature up to the maximum sintering temperature of each sample. The heating rate in all samples was set to 5 °C/min with 5 min dwell time at the maximum temperature (i.e. the original sintering temperature). The cooling rate was also set to 5 °C/min, but due to the thermal inertia of the equipment the temperature exhibits a non-linear decrease with time below 400 °C. Further details about the measurement can be found in our previously published papers [19,39,40].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of raw powders

Table 2 shows the results of the chemical composition of the raw powders determined via XRF. The experimentally measured values correspond nicely with the theoretical calculations of predicted chemical composition which should be 49 wt. % of Al₂O₃ and 48 wt. % of SiO₂ in the case of K80M20 and 52 wt. % Al₂O₃ and 45 wt. % SiO₂ for

Table 2

Chemical composition of the raw powders determined via XRF.

Oxide [wt. %]	Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	Other
K100M0	43.2	53.6	<4
K0M100	73.9	24.4	<4
K80M20	47.6	49.1	<4
K70M30	50.9	46.4	<4

K70M30 samples. The deviation in the experimental and calculated data is around 1 %, which is caused by the minor impurities present in the raw powders.

The crystalline phase composition of the raw powders is listed in Table 3 and the corresponding diffractograms are shown in Fig. 1. It is evident that the kaolin used here (Sedlec Ia) contains, apart from kaolinite, small amounts of other phases, mainly illite (or muscovite) and quartz, but also minor amounts of anatase and goyazite, which are in this way introduced into the K80M20 and K70M30 mixtures. On the other hand, the mullite used here (M72) introduces a small amount of corundum into the prepared mixtures.

Table 4 shows that the mullite (M72, here denoted as KOM100) has larger particle sizes and a broader size range than the kaolin (Sedlec Ia, here denoted as K100M0): for the kaolin the median size (D_{50}) is 4.2 μm and the arithmetic mean \bar{d} is 6.1 μm , while for the mullite the median size (D_{50}) is 6.3 μm , and the arithmetic mean \bar{d} is 8.1 μm ; the other deciles (D_{10} and D_{90}) give an impression of the width of the two distributions. Fig. 2 shows SEM micrographs of the two powders, which document the high degree of agglomeration of the kaolin and the presence of very small and rather larger particles and thus the quite broad size distribution of mullite.

3.2. Characterization of sintered bodies

Table 5 lists the results of XRD phase analysis of all prepared samples, including both the crystalline phases and the amorphous phase. Figs. 3 and 4 show the contents of amorphous phase and mullite, respectively, as functions of the sintering temperature. It is evident that the amorphous phase is in a reciprocal relation to the mullite content, i. e. when the amorphous phase content is high, the mullite content is low, and when the amorphous phase content decreases, the mullite content increases. The amorphous phase content is highest after sintering at 1100 °C, ranging between 48.5–80.4 wt. %, and lowest after sintering at 1400 °C. Above this temperature the amount is either slightly increasing (pure kaolin sample) or constant (kaolin-mullite mixtures). For the pure kaolin sample sintered in the range 1200–1400 °C, the absolute values of amorphous phase contents are 27–37 wt. %, which is in reasonable agreement with the values 30–35 wt. % found for the same material after sintering in the range 1250–1400 °C in our previous paper [19]. Moreover, these values are in reasonable agreement with the amorphous phase contents of 28–34 wt. % determined for refractories based on Algerian kaolin sintered in the range 1300–1450 °C by Kolli et al. [45], although the latter reported an increasing trend with sintering temperature. In pure kaolin samples the mullite content increases significantly with increasing sintering temperature up to 1400 °C. However, for a sintering temperature of 1500 °C, the mullite content decreases slightly, while the amorphous phase content increases. This indicates that at this temperature mullite dissolves in the amorphous phase. Our results also indicate that after sintering above 1200 °C quartz transforms into cristobalite, and the amorphous phase may also undergo recrystallization through the nucleation and growth of cristobalite. However, cristobalite disappears above 1400 °C, probably dissolving back into the glass phase, which may contribute to the increased amorphous phase content after sintering at 1500 °C. After sintering at 1100 °C, the major phase is amorphous phase, which is also evident from the diffraction patterns shown in Fig. 5, compared to Figs. 6 and 7. This high glass content is certainly not only due to the formation of amorphous silica but can be

Table 3

Crystalline phase composition of the initial powders determined via XRD.

Crys. phase [wt. %]	Kaolinite	Mullite	Illite	Quartz	Anatase	Goyazite	Corundum
K100M0	94.3	0.0	3.0	1.7	0.7	0.4	0.0
KOM100	0.0	95.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.2
K80M20	76.1	16.3	3.9	1.7	0.5	0.4	1.1
K70M30	65.9	27.2	3.2	1.5	0.4	0.3	1.5

Fig. 1. Diffraction patterns of raw powders and prepared mixtures.

Table 4

Particle size of the raw powders measured by laser diffraction.

	D10 [μm]	D50 [μm]	D90 [μm]	\bar{d} [μm]
K100M0	1.1	4.2	13.8	6.1
KOM100	0.9	6.3	18.6	8.1

assumed to be primarily due to the presence of a large amount of highly defective (non-crystalline or quasi-amorphous) Al-Si spinel phase resulting from the decomposition of metakaolinite (which is also “X-ray amorphous”) [46]. In the case of K80M20 and K70M30 samples the mullite content is of course higher and thus the amorphous phase content relatively lower, but still the highest amount of amorphous phase is observed after sintering at 1100 °C, as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. This is clearly due to the presence of a significant amount of defective Al-Si spinel phase that forms from metakaolinite (as in the pure kaolin

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of raw powders kaolin Sedlec Ia (left) and mullite M72 (right).

Table 5

Phase composition of sintered samples.

	T [°C]	Mullite [wt. %]	Quartz [wt. %]	Corundum [wt. %]	Cristobalite [wt. %]	Amorphous phase [wt. %]
K100M0	1100	18.3	1.6	0.0	0.0	80.4
	1200	59.7	2.0	0.0	1.2	37.0
	1300	64.7	0.7	0.0	7.1	27.4
	1400	65.2	0.4	0.0	0.0	26.7
	1500	61.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	38.1
K80M20	1100	34.3	1.6	3.4	0.0	60.7
	1200	62.6	2.4	2.6	3.6	28.7
	1300	67.0	1.0	1.1	4.6	26.3
	1400	70.6	0.0	0.9	4.5	23.8
	1500	71.5	0.0	0.8	0.0	27.8
K70M30	1100	42.5	1.5	7.5	0.0	48.5
	1200	65.4	2.3	2.4	3.0	26.8
	1300	67.1	1.2	1.3	3.2	27.2
	1400	71.7	0.3	1.0	2.9	24.1
	1500	74.6	0.0	0.8	0.0	24.5

Fig. 3. Amorphous phase content, determined via XRD, as a function of the sintering temperature.

sample) and is at higher sintering temperature transformed into mullite. A similar increase in the content of mullite formed from Al-Si spinel above 1100 °C has been observed for kaolin by in-situ high-temperature XRD [47]. At sintering temperatures higher than 1200 °C, the amorphous phase content does not change significantly, and quartz gradually disappears as it transforms into cristobalite. However, cristobalite is no longer present above 1400 °C, similar to the pure kaolin samples, probably because of the dissolution in the amorphous phase. Additionally, the amount of corundum decreases significantly, as Al₂O₃ either becomes incorporated into the mullite crystal lattice or reacts with SiO₂

Fig. 4. Mullite content, determined via XRD, as a function of the sintering temperature.

to form more mullite [46].

Fig. 8 shows a detailed view of selected diffraction lines for samples sintered at 1200 °C. Based on the shape of the diffraction lines, it is evident that the addition of mullite acts as a nucleating agent, facilitating further mullite formation. This is reflected in the fact that the diffraction lines in the K70M30 mixture are much more clearly separated. Additionally, a slight shift in the mullite diffraction lines can be observed, indicating that the mullite is not exactly stoichiometric, with slight variations in its lattice parameters.

Fig. 9 shows the linear shrinkage as a function of the sintering

Fig. 5. Diffraction patterns of pure kaolin samples sintered from 1100 °C to 1500 °C.

Fig. 8. Detailed view of selected diffraction lines of mullite and quartz for samples sintered at 1200 °C.

Fig. 6. Diffraction patterns of K80M20 samples sintered from 1100 °C to 1500 °C.

Fig. 7. Diffraction patterns of K70M30 samples sintered from 1100 °C to 1500 °C.

temperature. As expected, linear shrinkage increases with increasing sintering temperature. The absolute values are in the ranges 2.8–4.7 % and 11.5–12.9 % after sintering at 1100 °C and 1500 °C, respectively. Linear shrinkage decreases with increasing mullite content, since mullite is not subject to volume changes associated with reactions or

Fig. 9. Linear shrinkage as a function of the sintering temperature.

phase transformations and thus acts as a grog that prevents volume changes. Therefore, the higher the mullite content, the smaller the linear shrinkage.

In Fig. 10 the values of bulk density are presented as a function of the sintering temperature. The bulk density values range from 1.9 to 2.0 g·cm⁻³ after sintering at 1100 °C and from 2.6 to 2.7 g·cm⁻³ after sintering at 1500 °C. In the case of the pure kaolin sample, the bulk density does not increase when the sintering temperature exceeds 1400 °C, but slightly decreases, which may be related to the dissolution of crystalline

Fig. 10. Bulk density as a function of the sintering temperature.

phases (e.g. cristobalite) in the amorphous phase or with the release of gases (e.g. oxygen), a phenomenon that is known as “over-firing” [19].

Open porosity as a function of the sintering temperature is shown in Fig. 11. The open porosities range from 27.1 to 31.2 % after sintering at 1100 °C and from 0.4 to 3.9 % after sintering at 1500 °C. With higher mullite content, the open porosity increases, which can be explained by the fact that mullite forms a rigid skeleton, in the gaps of which the phase mixture arising from kaolin shrinks. For the pure kaolin sample, the open porosity is constant after sintering at 1400 and 1500 °C which is in nice agreement with the bulk density results.

Fig. 12 shows SEM micrographs (fracture surfaces) of samples sintered at 1100 °C, 1300 °C and 1500 °C. The micrographs shows a significant densification of samples at higher sintering temperatures and a “glassy” appearance after sintering at the highest temperature, but the microstructures of K80M20 and K70M30 samples are rather similar.

3.3. Elastic properties

Fig. 13 shows the room temperature values of Young’s modulus as a function of the sintering temperature. The values range from 20.7 to 25.7 GPa after sintering at 1100 °C and from 105.1 to 116.0 GPa after sintering at 1500 °C. It is evident that the sample prepared from pure kaolin and sintered at 1500 °C tends to deviate from the overall trend, confirming that firing temperatures of 1500 °C may not be suitable for pure kaolin samples, while it can lead to a significant improvement of the mechanical properties of kaolin-mullite mixtures.

Figs. 14 and 15 show the temperature dependences of Young’s modulus for samples K80M20 and K70M30, respectively, after firing to different temperatures, while Fig. 16 through Fig. 20 compare the results for samples K80M20 and K70M30 for each firing temperature separately. The latter representation reveals many details that cannot be seen in the former. An overall comparison shows that the Young’s modulus values for samples K80M20 fired at 1300 °C (range 71.4–75.6 GPa between RT and 1200 °C) are similar to pure kaolin samples after firing to 1250 °C (range 74–78 GPa), studied in previous work [19], for which the porosity is approximately the same (16 %), although the mullite content is higher and the glass phase content lower in the samples of the present work. Samples K70M30 fired at 1300 °C have significantly lower Young’s modulus (range 53.4–57.8 GPa between RT and 1200 °C) than the pure kaolin samples studied in previous work [19], although the mullite content is even higher and the glass phase content lower. The reason is that the porosity of these samples is significantly higher (20 %), see Fig. 11. Similar conclusions hold for samples after firing to 1400 °C. Also here the Young’s modulus values of samples K80M20 (range 105.0–111.6 GPa between RT and 1200 °C) are similar to (albeit slightly higher than) those of pure kaolin with 8 % porosity (range 98–102 GPa) [19], whereas that of K70M30 is

significantly lower (range 75.3–82.3 GPa between RT and 1200 °C). It is highly probable that apart from the difference in porosity, also microcracks affect these values. In particular, the significantly lower Young’s modulus values for samples K70M30 are likely to be caused by microcracks, which can appear during cooling due to the thermal mismatch stresses between mullite crystals and glass phase.

From Figs. 14 and 15 it is evident that after firing to 1100 °C the level of Young’s modulus is very similar for both types of samples. The comparative zoom in Fig. 16 shows that the values are in the range 20.5–22.5 GPa and are slightly (by less than 0.5 GPa) higher for K80M20 than for K70M30. This can be caused by the slightly lower porosity of K80M20, see Fig. 11, because the mullite content is higher and the glass phase content lower in K70M30 (which would otherwise lead to higher values of Young’s modulus if the porosity would be the same). Interestingly, in both cases there is a hysteresis between heating and cooling, i.e. the cooling curve is at a slightly higher level than the heating curve (between 200 and 800 °C by more than 1 GPa), and after cooling the Young’s modulus is slightly higher than before heating (by less than 1 GPa, however). Although this small difference is close to the precision limit of IET measurements, it might indicate a slight continuation of sintering, which is remarkable because the highest temperature during the IET measurement is not higher than the original firing temperature (1100 °C in both cases) and the dwell time is much shorter (5 min versus 2 h). This phenomenon could be caused by the higher heating rate (5 °C/min during the IET measurement versus 2 °C/min during firing) or by the fact that reactions in the system at this temperature are relatively slow and may still not be finished even after a 2 h dwell during firing. It should also be noted that despite the low residual quartz content which is lower than 2 wt. %, see Table 5, the quartz transition is clearly visible both during heating and cooling (albeit less during cooling than during heating). It has to be emphasized, however, that the quartz transition reveals itself only by a very slight effect in the IET measurements, in contrast to silicate ceramics with high quartz contents, where the quartz transition dominates the overall temperature dependence of Young’s modulus [36–38].

After firing at 1200 °C, see Fig. 17, the difference between the two sample types is significantly larger (approximately by 10 GPa, i.e. by one order of magnitude) than after firing to 1100 °C. This is clearly a consequence of the significantly lower porosity of samples K80M20 after firing at 1200 °C, see Fig. 11, because the phase composition is quite similar, see Table 5. Apart from the quartz transition, which is still visible, the curves reveal clear footprints of the cristobalite transition below 200 °C, which are well known from silica refractories [15,16]. This is in agreement with the XRD finding that cristobalite is present in the samples fired at 1200 °C, see Table 5. Also, in this case the aforementioned hysteresis between heating and cooling curves can be observed but there is no indication of a continuation of sintering during the IET measurement, because the hysteresis loops are closed. Above 1000 °C Young’s modulus decreases, which is of course related to the softening of the glass phase.

After firing at 1300, 1400 and 1500 °C, see Figs. 18, 19 and 20, respectively, new effects occur during the IET measurements at high temperature, including a local minimum at around 1200 °C (1150–1250 °C), above which Young’s modulus attains values of 60–70 GPa for all samples. Interestingly, after firing at 1300 °C, for the sample K80M20 a Young’s modulus value of ~60 GPa is attained by a decrease from a level of ~75 GPa, whereas for the sample K70M30 the same value is attained by an increase from a minimum of ~55 GPa. On the other hand, after firing at 1400 °C, a Young’s modulus value of ~65 GPa is attained for the sample K70M30 by a decrease from a level of around 80 GPa and for the sample K80M20 a slightly higher value (~67 GPa) by steep increase from a level of ~110 GPa and a minimum of ~105 GPa to values of ~120 GPa, followed by a stepwise discontinuity from ~120 GPa down to ~67 GPa. This stepwise discontinuity is reproduced (in the reverse direction, i.e. from ~70 GPa to ~120 GPa) also during cooling and occurs in the temperature range 1250–1300 °C. After firing at 1500 °C

Fig. 11. Open porosity as a function of the sintering temperature.

Fig. 12. SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of samples sintered at 1100 °C, 1300 °C and 1500 °C.

Fig. 13. Young's modulus as a function of the sintering temperature, measured at room temperature via the IET.

this scenario is similar for both sample types (K80M20 and K70M30): both samples show local minima in Young's modulus (106 and 99 GPa, respectively) at around 1150 °C, followed first by a steep increase to values of ~115 GPa at around 1270 °C and then by a stepwise discontinuity down to ~65 GPa and a slightly increasing trend towards ~70 GPa at 1500 °C. It should be noted in passing that after firing at 1500 °C the temperature dependence of Young's modulus does not show any indication of the cristobalite transition below 200 °C. This is in full agreement with the XRD finding that after firing at 1500 °C the samples do not contain cristobalite anymore, see Table 5. The quartz transition is not visible for samples fired at temperatures 1300 °C and higher, because after firing at these temperatures the quartz content falls below 1 % (and after firing at 1500 °C it is zero).

The most interesting feature in these temperature dependences of Young's modulus is without doubt the stepwise discontinuity at around 1270 °C, which is preceded by a steep increase of Young's modulus and

leads to a low, but more or less constant, Young's modulus at higher temperatures (up to 1500 °C). To the best of our knowledge this feature has not yet been described in the literature, although long-term experience in our laboratory has shown that it occurs relatively often in mullite- and glass-containing silicate ceramics (but never in non-silicate oxide ceramics without glass phase). The discontinuity is caused by a gradual peak splitting of the resonant frequency peak during the IET measurement and a concomitant change in the intensity (height) of these peaks as a function of the temperature. The high-frequency part of the splitted peak is shifted to higher frequencies with increasing temperature, thus indicating an increase in Young's modulus. At the same time, however, its intensity (height) decreases significantly and may finally vanish completely. Concomitantly with these effects the low-frequency part of the splitted peak increases in intensity, until it is finally the only significant part left of the resonant frequency peak. During a short transitional stage the system behaves as if it would have

Fig. 14. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for samples K80M20 prepared by firing to 1100, 1200, 1300, 1400 and 1500 °C.

Fig. 15. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for samples K70M30 prepared by firing to 1100, 1200, 1300, 1400 and 1500 °C.

two resonant frequencies. This case should not occur in classical continuum mechanics. Therefore, in practice, the result is a discontinuity in the temperature dependence of Young's modulus as determined by the IET measurement. (It has to be emphasized that here we are talking exclusively about the fundamental mode of the resonant frequency of flexural vibrations, i.e. not about higher harmonics and not about other types of vibrations). A transitional stage where two resonant frequencies occur simultaneously can only be explained when it is assumed that in this stage there are two decoupled continua that can vibrate to a certain degree independently.

The aforementioned phenomena can be explained when it is assumed that when the glass phase softens the material behaves

essentially as a two-phase system consisting of an interconnected mullite skeleton (67–75 wt. %) and an interskeletal glassy phase (24–28 wt. %). As soon as this glass phase softens significantly, i.e. enters the viscoelastic regime in the temperature range 800–1200 °C, it is possible that the flexural vibrations of the interconnected mullite skeleton, which is purely elastic, can be decoupled from the flexural vibrations of the glassy phase, which may at high temperature resemble a viscous glass melt (with only minor elastic contributions to the overall behavior). Although mullite has a significantly higher Young's modulus than glass, the reason for the increase in Young's modulus with increasing temperature should rather be sought in the possibility of the glass melt to heal pre-existent microcracks. This seems to be the case for temperatures

Fig. 16. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for samples K80M20 and K70M30 prepared by firing to 1100 °C.

Fig. 17. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for samples K80M20 and K70M30 prepared by firing to 1200 °C.

below ~1270 °C. Above this temperature, all IET results indicate that the mullite-mullite bonds are loosened so that the mullite skeleton loses its interconnectivity and the material changes its microstructure from bicontinuous to a matrix-inclusion type microstructure, in which glass forms the matrix and the mullite crystals (together with the other crystalline phases) the inclusions. It is plausible that such a material, in which the mullite crystals are just inclusions in a soft glass phase (melt), has a significantly lower Young's modulus than a material in which the mullite crystals form an interconnected skeleton.

4. Conclusions

In this paper the temperature dependence of the Young's modulus kaolin-based silicate ceramics with mullite addition fired at 1100, 1200, 1300, 1400 and 1500 °C is investigated during heating and cooling using the impulse excitation technique (IET). This is a model system for high-alumina refractories.

In summary, it can be said that with increasing mullite addition the Young's modulus of kaolin-mullite-based materials does not increase but decreases, although mullite has a higher Young's modulus than the glass

Fig. 18. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for samples K80M20 and K70M30 prepared by firing to 1300 °C.

Fig. 19. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for samples K80M20 and K70M30 prepared by firing to 1400 °C.

phase, quartz and cristobalite. The reason for this is the fact that concomitantly with the increase in the mullite content also the porosity increases, because mullite acts as a grog and, when added in sufficient amounts, forms an interconnected skeleton that prevents densification. After sintering at 1100 and 1200 °C the quartz transition at around 573 °C can be clearly identified in the temperature dependence of Young's modulus, while the cristobalite transition below 200 °C is visible only after firing at 1200, 1300 and 1400 °C, but not after firing at 1500 °C, where cristobalite is absent in the materials. This is in excellent agreement with the results of XRD phase analysis.

The most interesting finding of this paper concerns the temperature dependence of Young's modulus at temperatures around 1200 °C, where a minimum is observed, followed by a steep increase to ~120 GPa and a stepwise discontinuity at ~1270 °C to a final values of 60–70 GPa, which are retained up to 1500 °C. This peculiar behavior can be explained by the assumption that on the one hand the glass melt is able to heal pre-existent microcracks and on the other hand the softening of the glass phase leads to a splitting of the resonant frequency peak, i.e. a decoupling of the flexural vibrations of the interconnected mullite skeleton (67–75 wt. %) and the interskeletal glassy phase (24–28 wt. %), which

Fig. 20. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for samples K80M20 and K70M30 prepared by firing to 1500 °C.

finally leads to a discontinuity when the mullite crystals become disconnected and the microstructure of the material changes from bicontinuous to matrix-inclusion type.

Data availability statement

The original raw data for this paper are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13961384>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Petra Šimonová: Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Eva Gregorová:** Visualization, Validation, Investigation. **Willi Pabst:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Daria Viazun:** Investigation. **Petr Bezdicka:** Investigation.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This paper was created as part of the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of the Czech Republic (via the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports).

References

- [1] S. Kienow, F. Harders. *Feuerfestkunde*, Springer, Berlin, 1960.
- [2] J. Wu, Z. Zhang, X. Xu, S. Ma, P. Li, X. Shi, Preparation and thermal shock resistance of mullite ceramics for high temperature solar thermal storage, *J. Wuhan Univ. Technol.-Mater. Sci. Ed.* 38 (4) (2023) 743–752.
- [3] X. Xu, Y. Shen, J. Wu, Z. Zhang, J. Yu, S. Qiu, The thermal shock resistance of in-situ synthesized mullite absorption and storage integrated ceramics for solar thermal power generation, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (5) (2024) 7843–7852.
- [4] H. Cheng, F. Ye, J. Chang, S. Wu, In situ synthesis and thermal shock resistance of a cordierite-mullite composite for solar thermal storage, *Int. J. Appl. Ceram. Technol.* 16 (2) (2019) 772–780.
- [5] Y. Deng, X. Lao, X. Xu, Z. Mao, Y. Zhao, Y. Li, A cost-effective way to utilize low-grade Ti-rich clay: preparing cordierite-mullite composite ceramics for thermal storage, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (20B) (2024) 39059–39068.
- [6] X. Xu, Y. Zhang, J. Wu, C. Hu, Z. Tang, Preparation and performance study of cordierite/mullite composite ceramics for solar thermal energy storage, *Int. J. Appl. Ceram. Technol.* 14 (2) (2017) 162–172.
- [7] M. Omerasević, M. Krsmanović, Ž. Radovanović, D. Bučevac, Mechanical properties and thermal shock resistance of anorthite ceramics obtained by slip casting, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (3B) (2024) 5787–5795.
- [8] J. Wu, J. Yu, X. Xu, Y. Liu, Z. Zhang, P. Wei, Preparation and thermal shock resistance of anorthite solar thermal energy storage ceramics from magnesium slag, *Ceram. Int.* 48 (22) (2022) 33604–33614.
- [9] J. Liu, Y. Zhang, Z. Su, D. Huang, D. Xu, M. Lu, S. Liu, T. Jiang, Novel low-cost anorthite porous ceramic-based binary chlorate high-temperature thermal energy storage material: preparation and characterization, *Energy Fuels* 35 (15) (2021) 12425–12435.
- [10] N. Huda, M.A. Whitney, M.H. Razmpoosh, A.P. Gerlich, J.Z. Wen, S.F. Corbin, How phase (α and γ) and porosity affect specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity of thermal storage alumina, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 104 (3) (2021) 1436–1447.
- [11] Z. Cai, Y. Li, S. Li, H. Wu, C. Bai, J. Tan, X. Xu, Y. Yin, W. Wang, Novel high thermal conductivity alumina/salt composites for thermal energy storage: effect of wettability on microstructure and properties, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 44 (6) (2024) 3953–3964.
- [12] X. Xu, X. Lao, J. Wu, Y. Zhang, X. Xu, K. Li, Synthesis and characterization of Al₂O₃/SiC composite ceramics via carbothermal reduction of aluminosilicate precursor for solar sensible thermal storage, *J. Alloys Compd.* 662 (2016) 126–137.
- [13] X. Lao, X. Xu, W. Jiang, J. Liang, H. Liu, A simple and clean method to prepare SiC-containing vitreous ceramics for solar thermal storage in the clay-feldspar system, *J. Clean. Prod.* 248 (2020) 119257.
- [14] A.R. Sane, P.-M. Nigay, D. Pham Minh, C. Toussaint, A. Germeau, N. Semlal, R. Boulif, A. Nzihou, An investigation of the physical, thermal and mechanical properties of fired clay/SiC ceramics for thermal energy storage, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 140 (5) (2020) 2087–2096.
- [15] E. Gregorová, L. Kotrbová, W. Pabst, Thermal cycling damage of silica refractories for high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) – Can it be healed? *Open Ceramics* 19 (2024) 100658.
- [16] E. Gregorová, W. Pabst, P. Šimonová, V. Nečina, L. Kotrbová, P. Bezdicka, J. Hubáková, G. Schmidt, C.G. Aneziris, I. Sedlářová, M. Kotouček, Temperature dependence of Young's modulus, damping and dilatation during repeated thermal cycling of silica refractories for high-temperature thermal energy storage (TES), *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 45 (2) (2024) 116946.
- [17] ASTM, C1259-01: Standard test method for dynamic Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio for advanced ceramics by impulse excitation of vibration, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, 2001.
- [18] ASTM, E1876-01: Standard test method for dynamic Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio by impulse excitation of vibration, West Conshohocken, 2001.

- [19] E. Gregorová, W. Pabst, P. Šimonová, P. Bezdička, V. Nečina, Evolution of Young's modulus and damping of Czech kaolins during sintering monitored via impulse excitation, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 44 (11) (2024) 6721–6742.
- [20] P. Pialy, N. Tessier-Doyen, D. Njopwouo, J.-P. Bonnet, Effects of densification and mullitization on the evolution of the elastic properties of a clay-based material during firing, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 29 (9) (2009) 1579–1586.
- [21] I. Štubňa, A. Trník, L. Vozár, Thermomechanical and thermomechanical analysis of green alumina porcelain, *Ceram. Int.* 35 (3) (2009) 1181–1185.
- [22] I. Štubňa, A. Trník, R. Podoba, R. Sokolar, P. Bacik, Elastic properties of waste calcite-clay ceramics during firing, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.* 120 (1405) (2012) 351–354.
- [23] H.T. Jankula M, I. Štubňa, J. Ondruška, R. Podoba, P. Šín, P. Bačík, A. Trník, The influence of heat on elastic properties of illitic clay Radobica, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.* 123 (1441) (2015) 874–879.
- [24] T. Húlan, T. Kaljuvee, I. Štubňa, A. Trník, Investigation of elastic and inelastic properties of Estonian clay from a locality in Kunda during thermal treatment, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 124 (3) (2016) 1153–1159.
- [25] I. Štubňa, T. Húlan, T. Kaljuvee, L. Vozár, Investigation of dynamic mechanical properties of Estonian clay Arumetsa during firing, *Appl. Clay Sci.* 153 (2018) 23–28.
- [26] A. Trník, Use of fly ash in ceramic tiles: elastic properties during firing, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.* 121 (1419) (2013) 925–929.
- [27] P.M. Nigay, T. Cutard, A. Nzihou, The impact of heat treatment on the microstructure of a clay ceramic and its thermal and mechanical properties, *Ceram. Int.* 43 (2) (2017) 1747–1754.
- [28] T. Húlan, A. Trník, T. Kaljuvee, M. Uibu, I. Štubňa, U. Kallavus, R. Traksmaa, The study of firing of a ceramic body made from illite and fluidized bed combustion fly ash, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 127 (1) (2017) 79–89.
- [29] A. Trník, I. Štubňa, J. Moravčíková, Sound velocity of kaolin in the temperature range from 20 °C to 1100 °C, *Int. J. Thermophys.* 30 (4) (2009) 1323–1328.
- [30] I. Štubňa, P. Sin, A. Trník, R. Veinthal, Mechanical properties of kaolin during heating, *Key Eng. Mater.* 527 (2012) 14–19.
- [31] C.R.E. Aston S. D, G.P. Yiasemides, The dependence of the elastic properties of silica /alumina materials on the conditions used for firing, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 22 (2002) 1119–1127.
- [32] M.F. Serra, M.F. Acebedo, M.S. Conconi, G. Suarez, E.F. Aglietti, N.M. Rendtorff, Thermal evolution of the mechanical properties of calcareous earthenware, *Ceram. Int.* 40 (1B) (2014) 1709–1716.
- [33] M.F. Serra, M.S. Conconi, G. Suarez, E.F. Aglietti, N.M. Rendtorff, Volcanic ash as flux in clay based triaxial ceramic materials, effect of the firing temperature in phases and mechanical properties, *Ceram. Int.* 41 (5A) (2015) 6169–6177.
- [34] D. Antal, T. Húlan, I. Štubňa, M. Záleská, A. Trník, The influence of texture on elastic and thermophysical properties of kaolin- and illite-based ceramic bodies, *Ceram. Int.* 43 (2) (2017) 2730–2736.
- [35] V.-G. Lee, T.-H. Yeh, Sintering effects on the development of mechanical properties of fired clay ceramics, *Mater. Sci. Eng.: A* 485 (1) (2008) 5–13.
- [36] T. Húlan, I. Štubňa, T. Kaljuvee, M. Knappek, Young's modulus of illitic clay in the temperature region of quartz transition, *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 147 (14) (2022) 7701–7707.
- [37] A.P.N.d. Oliveira, E.S. Vilches, V.C. Soler, F.A.G. Villegas, Relationship between Young's modulus and temperature in porcelain tiles, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 32 (11) (2012) 2853–2858.
- [38] M. Dal Bó, V. Cantavella, E. Sánchez, F.A. Gilabert, A.O. Boschi, D. Hotza, An estimate of quartz content and particle size in porcelain tiles from young's modulus measurements, *Ceram. Int.* 43 (2) (2017) 2233–2238.
- [39] E. Gregorová, P. Šimonová, W. Pabst, T. Uhlířová, V. Nečina, Temperature dependence of Young's modulus and the occurrence of an elastic anomaly in porous alumina-mullite composites prepared by starch consolidation casting, *Ceram. Int.* 50 (4) (2024) 6309–6323.
- [40] E. Gregorová, P. Šimonová, W. Pabst, Temperature dependence of Young's modulus and damping of uniaxially pressed and partially sintered mullite ceramics and mullite-alumina composites, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 44 (2) (2024) 1081–1094.
- [41] T. Degen, M. Sadki, E. Bron, U. König, G. Nénert, The HighScore Powder Diffraction 29 (S2) (2014) S13–S18.
- [42] H. Rietveld, A profile refinement method for nuclear and magnetic structures, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 2 (2) (1969) 65–71.
- [43] N. Doebelin, R. Kleeberg, Profex: a graphical user interface for the Rietveld refinement program BGMN, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 48 (5) (2015) 1573–1580.
- [44] K. Ufer, R. Kleeberg, T. Monecke, Quantification of stacking disordered Si-Al layer silicates by the Rietveld method: application to exploration for high-sulphidation epithermal gold deposits, *Powder Diffr.* 30 (2015) 111–118.
- [45] M. Kolli, M. Hamidouche, G. Fantozzi, J. Chevalier, Elaboration and characterization of a refractory based on Algerian kaolin, *Ceram. Int.* 33 (8) (2007) 1435–1443.
- [46] S. Komarneni, H. Schneider. Mullite, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2005.
- [47] P. Štursa, D. Všianský, K. Lang, L. Nevřivová, L. Tvrđík, P. Kovář, L. Keršnerová, Effects of crystallinity on high-temperature phase transitions of kaolinite, *Geologické výzkumy na Moravě a ve Slezsku* 27 (2020) 21–26.